

PARTICULATE METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT FOR I.C. ENGINE PISTON APPLICATION

S. Sundararajan*, R. Mahadevan* and E. S. Dwarakadasa

Structure Property Correlations group

Department of Metallurgy, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore 560 012, India

* India Pistons Limited, Huzur Gardens, Sembiam. Madras 600 011, India

ABSTRACT

Liquid metallurgy stir cast technique has been employed to obtain a distribution of 14 and 28 μm SiC_p in an aluminium base IC engine piston material. Distribution of SiC_p in the composite as observed on random metallographic sections greatly improved by either addition of magnesium metal just prior to introducing the ceramic particles and/or by prior mixing of the ceramic with a mixture of zirconia and magnesia of a proprietary composition. Prior heating of the ceramic further improved the distribution. Problems encountered in obtaining a good distribution were identified as casting problems to be avoided by proper design of the casting process. Cast MMC slugs could be either directly machined or forged initially and then machined to final dimensions of piston geometry. Presence of SiC_p and the oxide mixture slightly accelerated the thermal aging response and significantly improved the thermal stability and the elastic modulus. The MMC produced has been characterized for use as an IC engine piston material to point out the advantages and disadvantages. Examination of tensile fracture surfaces pointed to improved bonding of the particle to the matrix. During forging, particles moved in the direction of plastic flow without breakage or debonding. The overall objective of the project is to produce cost effective MMC material with superior properties for IC engine piston application.

INTRODUCTION

The Material revolution has had its impact on the automobile industry as well in recent years. The pistons which were made of cast iron are now made of lighter aluminium-silicon alloys. The designers of pistons are always on the look out for newer materials with better strength/weight ratio and improved thermal and mechanical stability in the crown and combustion bowl areas and better wear resistance particularly in the ring groove areas[1]. Metal matrix composite(MMC) is one such material which promises solutions to problems faced by the piston manufacturers. MMC materials fabricated through cast route contain several casting defects like porosity, segregation, agglomeration of the reinforcement, etc. necessitating secondary processing of the MMC material to overcome these problems. Since the pistons are fabricated both by as-cast and forging routes, composite pistons were made by forging and subsequent machining in this work. MMC's promise considerable improvement in the modulus and thermal properties[2]. They also exhibit accelerated aging behaviour compared with that in the unreinforced alloy[3]. The objective of this work is to characterize the physical and mechanical properties, heat treatment cycle and the forgeability of

Al-12Si-SiC_P MMCs. Composite pistons machined out of forged slugs seem to display a good potential.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Al-12Si-10SiC_P composite materials were fabricated by stir cast route with a ceramic coated steel impeller[4] using SiC particules of average size 28 μm . The SiC_P was thoroughly mixed with a mixture of zirconia and magnesia of proprietary composition[5] and suitably preheated before adding to the melt. A monolithic alloy of the same chemical composition as the matrix of the MMC was also prepared under similar conditions for the purposes of comparison. A typical composition range of the Al-12 Si alloy is given in Table I. The monolithic alloy and the MMC were gravity cast in permanent moulds in the form of slugs of dimension 95 mm dia x 100 mm ht.(Fig. 1).

Table I. Typical Composition of the Al-12Si Alloy

Element	Si	Cu	Mg	Ni	Fe
Wt. %	11.8	1.00	2.50	0.80	< 0.8

Fig. 1: Typical MMC slug obtained by the Stir Cast Route

Young's Modulus, UTS and Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

The Young's Modulus of the Al-12Si alloy and the Al-12Si-10SiC_P composite material were measured through acoustic emission technique using an 'Elastosonic' microprocessor based instrument. Tensile tests were carried out on standard test specimens on an Instron Model 8032 universal testing machine using a strain rate of 10^{-2}s^{-1} . The Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) was measured in the range 300-600K in a Mettler TA 3000 TGA system.

Age Hardening

10 mm thick slices cut from the cylindrical castings from the pencil moulds were subjected to artificial aging. Samples were Solutionised at 773 K for 1 h followed by rapid quenching in water at room temperature. They were then aged at 433, 453, 473 and 493 K for 25 h. Aging curves were established by monitoring the Vickers hardness(HV0.1, average of 8-10 readings) taken at regular intervals.

Composite Forging

The composite slugs were forged in a Lombard Forge press. Slugs were preheated to about 773 K before forging. Other forging parameters were similar to those used for the monolithic material used in normal practice. After forging, they were sectioned longitudinally and prepared for metallographic examination in a standard way by grinding on emery papers and polishing on rotating wheels charged with diamond paste. Etching the polished section with 0.2% HF solution enabled the observation of the flow pattern in the material during forging as well as the distribution of the SiC particles. Using a linear intercept method the average interparticle distance between SiC particles was measured[6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Young's Modulus, UTS and Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

The Al-12Si-10SiC_p composite was observed to show an increase in the Young's Modulus by about 5% compared with that of the monolithic material (Table II). This increase of about 5% in the modulus of the composite is in accordance with the rule of mixtures[7]. In terms of UTS the composite material exhibits a 15% higher value than the monolithic material. However, the coefficient of thermal expansion of the composite is found to be marginally lower than that of the unreinforced material(Table II). This is understandable since the rule of mixtures also predicts only a marginal change for a composite containing 10% SiC_p. The improvement in the UTS of the composite in spite of the presence of casting defects like gas and shrinkage porosities appears to indicate good bonding of the reinforcement with the matrix. This is confirmed from the observation of the SEM fractographs(Fig. 2 a-c). These fractographs indicate that the mechanism of failure does not include particle debonding from the matrix and the matrix has failed by ductile rupture.

Table II. Some properties of unreinforced alloy and the composite

Material	Modulus, GPa	CTE, $\times 10^{-5}K^{-1}$ 300-373 K	UTS, MPa
Pure Al	72	2.4	55
Al-12Si alloy	78	2.35	250.0
Al-12Si-10%SiC _p	82	2.32	289.4

Aging Behaviour

Hardness vs. aging time plots for the monolithic and the composite material as a function of aging temperature is shown in Fig. 3 and 4. The composite material exhibits a somewhat accelerated aging behaviour relative to that of the monolithic material. The peak hardness achieved in the composite is significantly higher than that obtained in the monolithic material. It increases with decreasing aging temperatures(Fig. 5) both in the composite as well as in the monolithic material. Fig 6 gives a comparison of the time-to-peak vs. aging temperature for the two materials. It is interesting to note that the hardness in the as quenched condition is higher in the composite compared with that in the monolithic alloy.

The accelerated aging behaviour observed in the MMC could be attributed to the increase in the matrix dislocation density due to the difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion of the Al-12Si matrix($23 \times 10^{-6}K^{-1}$) and that of SiC_p($3 \times 10^{-6}K^{-1}$). The increased matrix hardness at lower

Fig. 2: Secondary electron micrographs of the tensile fracture surfaces of the composite; (a) and (b) showing the particle of SiC and (c) matrix region.

Fig. 3: Hardness Vs. aging time plot for the unreinforced alloy

Fig. 4: Hardness vs. aging time plot for the composite material

Fig. 5: Plot of peak hardness vs. aging temperature for the MMC and the monolithic material

Fig. 6: Plot of time-to-peak vs. aging temperature for MMC and the monolithic material

aging temperatures could be attributed to the dominance of shearing of precipitates in the matrix by dislocations whereas at higher aging temperatures the dominance of particle bowing mechanism leads to lower peak hardness[8]. The shorter time to achieve peak hardness at higher aging temperatures in both cases is obviously due to the higher diffusion rates of the quenched-in vacancies. It is to be pointed out that the composite material exhibits a remarkable thermal stability in the post-peak period. There is very little overaging observed in the composite material, whereas in the monolithic material there is a significant amount of overaging. Over long aging periods upto 25 h the hardness of the monolithic material dropped significantly while that of the composite material remained almost at the same peak value.

Composite Forging

A machined piston from the composite forging is shown in Fig. 7. The flow pattern in the longitudinal sections of the composite material forging with SiC_p of 14 and 28 μm sizes are shown in Fig. 8(a) and (b) respectively. The distribution of SiC_p in these forgings shown in photomicrograph in Fig. 9 for a typical case seems to be good and uniform. Histograms showing the average interparticle distance of SiC particles in these forgings are given in Fig. 10.

It is observed that the composite forgings are free from visual defects such as cracks, porosity, etc.(Fig. 8). A uniform distribution of SiC_p could be achieved as is evident from micrographs 10 a and b and Fig. 11. This can be attributed to the effective role played by the fine particle oxide

mixture in influencing the distribution of SiC_p in the molten Al-12Si alloy as well as during the solidification of the alloy.

Fig. 7: a machined Al-12Si-SiC composite piston

Fig. 8: Flow pattern of composite forgings with SiC particle sizes (a) 14 μm and (b) 28 μm

Fig. 9: Distribution of SiC particles in the composite forgings, SiC particle size: 28 μm

Fig. 10: Average interparticle distance of SiC in the composite forgings

SiC_P Distribution

While making a few tens of pistons, it was realized that the entire process of SiC_P distribution is controlled more by the skill of the operator, mainly because of the difficulty in adjusting the umpteen number of complex parameters. What it actually points to is that the entire process of dispersing SiC_P is a function of a number of interdependent parameters and these are all varying continuously and are correlated to one another in a complicated way. One needs to study the process in detail to be effective in being able to control every one of the parameters. A complete analysis of the stir-cast process has been discussed elsewhere[9-11].

A dramatic improvement in the distribution of SiC_P takes place on addition of the oxide mixture SiC_P prior to its addition to the melt. At this time it is yet unclear as to the role played by either MgO or by ZrO₂ or both. Work is under progress to study this aspect in detail.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Significant increase has been observed in the Young's Modulus and UTS of the Al-12Si-10SiC_P composite material compared with those of the unreinforced alloy while the coefficient of thermal expansion does not change significantly.
2. Thermal aging behaviour is accelerated in the composite material relative to that in the monolithic alloy and is attributable to the increase in matrix dislocation density due to the thermal mismatch between the matrix and the reinforcement.
3. Tensile fracture surfaces indicate the ductile rupture of the matrix and absence of particle debonding from the matrix.
4. Defect-free composite forgings could be made under similar conditions used for the unreinforced alloy.
5. A uniform distribution of SiC_P can be achieved both in the as cast and forged conditions and is further enhanced by the addition of a zirconia/magnesia mixture of proprietary composition to the SiC_P prior to introduction into the melt.

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